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Project Deliverable

D8.3: Report on exposures which lead to epigenetic age acceleration or deceleration

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Executive Summary

Aging is a key risk factor for many diseases, including cancer, and a better understanding of its underlying molecular mechanisms may help to prevent, delay, or treat age-related pathologies. Epigenetic alterations such as DNA methylation (DNAm) changes are a hallmark of aging and form the basis of epigenetic clocks, yet their functional relevance in disease is often unclear.

We defined 22 functional epigenetic clocks by overlapping age-related CpG sites found to be located within 200 bp from the transcription start site of a gene occupied by PCGTs, sites significantly altered after inhibition of proliferation (either increased or reduced), or senescence. Data for each clock was applied to 18 previously described epigenetic datasets and a new dataset from a mouse methylation study.

Our findings offer insights into the association of functionally enriched groups of age-related DNAm changes with cancer, identify sites perturbed earliest during carcinogenesis, and those distinct between cancer and reprogramming that could inform strategies to prevent teratoma formation upon in vivo reprogramming. Surprisingly, both mouse and human data reveal accelerated aging in breast cancer tissue but decelerated epigenetic aging in some non-cancer surrogate samples from breast cancer patients, in particular cervical samples.

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1 Introduction

Epigenetic changes are a hallmark of aging and cancer and form the basis of many proposed biomarkers of aging. Still, the biological interpretation of the changes in the context of pathology is often lacking. Some age-related epigenetic changes may likely be causes of aging, some may be consequences of aging, and depending on cell type and genomic location, aging may contribute to different cellular phenotypic states and functions.

To better characterize epigenetic aging and understand factors linked to age acceleration or deceleration, we have explored links between cell-type-specific age-related DNA methylation (DNAm) changes at CpGs linked with key hallmarks of aging and cancer.

In this deliverable, we outline work to characterize the behaviour of functional groups of age-related epigenetic changes. We leveraged DNAm data from cancer tissue or at risk of developing cancer and anatomically distant 'surrogate' tissues. Our focus is on women's cancers due to the availability of a large dataset of surrogate samples from current cancer cases, as well as the availability of samples during preneoplastic stages.

In the final stage, we validated findings from observational human data with a mouse model of breast carcinogenesis with or without chemoprevention, allowing for the study of DNAm changes in multiple organs from the same individual.

2 Methods

2.1 Datasets and data processing

We used 18 previously described, openly available epigenetic datasets with associated metadata and a new mouse methylation study.

Except for data from The Cancer Genome Atlas (TCGA), raw IDAT methylation files were preprocessed using a previously described pipeline made available under <https://www.github.com/chiaraherzog/eutopsQC>. For mouse data, manifest and annotation packages compatible with this pipeline, based on minfi and ChAMP, were generated and are publicly available (<https://github.com/chiaraherzog/IlluminaMouseMethylationmanifest>, <https://github.com/chiaraherzog/IlluminaMouseMethylationanno.12.v1.mm10>). Processed TCGA methylation data were accessed using TCGAbiolinks, version 2.28.3.

2.2 Definition of functional ageing clocks

CpGs associated with each of the following hallmarks of aging and cancer were identified and evaluated: senescence, promoter methylation at genes associated with stem cell fate (polycomb group target genes, PCGTs), and dysregulated proliferation.

We defined functional clocks by overlapping age-related CpG sites found to be located within 200 bp from the transcription start site of a gene occupied by PCGTs, sites significantly altered after inhibition of proliferation (either increased or reduced), or senescence.

Clocks for each of the 22 groups of CpGs were calculated for each dataset (Figure). We also computed 3 previously described epigenetic clocks for each dataset: Hannum clock, Horvath clock, and PhenoAge. The computation used information provided by the original authors.

Fig. 1 Development of cell type-specific functionally enriched DNAm aging clocks.

Age-related DNAm changes may be elicited, amongst other factors, by the overall aging process, cell type-specific processes, functional changes relating to aging, and the interplay between these three aspects. Here, we aimed to develop functionally enriched DNAm signatures indicative of one or more of these aspects by identifying overlapping CpGs, and evaluated these signatures in a variety of contexts.

b Overlaps utilized for the development of CpG signatures. Icons from Biorender.com.

2.3 Mouse study and ageing signatures

Mouse data were from experiments performed by our team in the context of a project with separate funding (European Research Council Advanced Grant: BRCA-ERC; project number 742432). Methylation data were generated by the EU Translational Oncology Prevention and Screening Institute facility (University of Innsbruck). For the mouse, no matched expression and methylation data were available, and hence we were not able to define human-equivalent proliferation or senescence clocks. PCGT genes were identified using the same list as for human data and mouse PCGT CpGs identified by filtering the annotation of the Illumina Methylation mouse array for murine PCGT gene symbol orthologs, keeping only genes located within 200 bp of a transcription start site (TSS200) and unmethylated in fetal mouse tissue (mean beta < 0.2 across n=41 fetal samples from the mouse methylation atlas (NCBI GEO GSE184410), including fetal brain (n=11), intestine (n=9), limb (n=10), and liver (n=11)). Age-related sites were correlated with age (cor > 0.2, p.adjust < 0.05) or not correlated with age (|cor| < 0.2) across several mouse tissues (n=87), including breast, oviduct, cervix, adipose tissue, blood, liver, spleen, and others, were identified, correcting for tissue type. Any sites on X, Y, or MT (mitochondrial) chromosomes were excluded.

2.4 Data availability

Data used in this study can be accessed from the NCBI Gene Expression Omnibus, the TCGA GDC Portal, or the European Genome-Phenome Archive, with the exception of data from the NSHD MRC 1946 birth cohort due to data privacy. NSHD MRC1946 methylation and clinical data are available to bona fide researchers upon request to the Data Sharing Committee via a standard application procedure. Further details can be found at <https://skylark.ucl.ac.uk/NSHD/doku.php?id=home>.

2.5 Code availability

Code to fully reproduce the findings in this study will be made available when the study results are published: https://github.com/chiaraherzog/functional_ageing_sigs/.

3 Results

We defined 22 functional ageing signatures comprised of groups of CpGs correlated with age in different cell types, and associated with senescence, PCGT methylation, or dysregulated proliferation.

Data are presented and discussed in *Herzog CMS, Redl E, Barrett J, Aminzadeh-Gohari S, Weber DD, Tevini J, Lang R, Kofler B, Widschwendter M. Functionally enriched epigenetic clocks reveal tissue-specific discordant*

aging patterns in individuals with cancer. Commun Med (Lond). 2025 Apr 2;5(1):98. doi: 10.1038/s43856-025-00739-4. PMID: 40175686; PMCID: PMC11965555.

4 Summary

Research presented in this deliverable provides initial insights into functional modules of age-related and cell type-specific DNAm sites and their association with current and future cancer in tissue at risk or surrogate samples. Our study also evaluates the impact of risk-increasing or reducing exposures on age-associated features and evaluates the predictive power of functional modules.

To our knowledge, our study is the first to comprehensively investigate functionally enriched modules of age-related and cell-type-specific DNAm sites associated with senescence, proliferation, and stem cell fate, and their association with current and future cancer in tissue at risk or surrogate samples. We define groups of CpGs associated with these hallmarks, and independently validate their association with mRNA expression levels of senescence- and proliferation-associated genes. Our study also evaluates the impact of risk-increasing or reducing exposures on age-associated features. It evaluates the predictive power of functional modules for response to chemotherapy and all-cause mortality. In contrast to previous studies, our study did not involve training predictors for cumulative population doubling, chronological age, time-to-death, or cancer. Instead, it used mean weighted methylation values of subgroups of CpGs moderately correlated with chronological age and associated with senescence, dysregulated proliferation, or stem cell fate, to construct functionally-enriched clocks.

This unbiased approach without a strong focus on chronological age or any specific outcome, such as mortality, as well as the comprehensive evaluation of signatures across a variety of independent datasets, populations, and multiple species (human and mouse), are strengths of the study. Notably, the modules described in the current study exhibit distinct behaviours over the course of cellular reprogramming, providing insights into the connection of age-related DNAm sites and reprogramming. We note that age acceleration and deceleration remain challenging to interpret. The purpose of the current study was not to develop optimal clocks. Instead, we anticipate that our benchmarking of functionally enriched clocks, including a comparison to commonly leveraged existing clocks, across several exposures and age-related pathologies, can help to elucidate systemic changes occurring under these conditions. In the future, this may help to

develop better clocks and/or understanding of epigenetic changes with aging and cancer.

We are currently working to apply the clocks to the lifestyle study data, which was also generated as part of the HEAP project in WP8. The lifestyle study has involved comprehensive DNAm analysis of approximately 1,700 samples from 156 women who provided samples over a 6-month period while they engaged in intermittent fasting (with or without ketogenic supplement) or smoking cessation (where applicable), accompanied by an optional exercise program. Data on other omics and clinical features were also collected.